

Effect of Dilution, Dialysis and Non-electrolytes on the Coagulation Constants of Stannic Hydroxide Sol

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Coagulation constants, 'a', 'm' and 'n' of Bhattacharya's equation for stannic hydroxide sol, at various stages of dilution and dialysis and as well as in presence of non-electrolytes, have been studied during its slow coagulation using NaCl and KCl as coagulants. The progressive dialysis has been found to cause a marked decrease in the value of each constant. Addition of increasing volume of sensitizing non-electrolytes (ethanol, acetone and dioxane) causes a decrease in the values of a, (a+m), and n and the reverse effect is obtained with stabilising non-electrolytes (glycerol and urea).

In continuation of our previous publications¹ on ferric hydroxide sol, we have extended our studies on the coagulation of stannic hydroxide sol. The present communication deals with an attempt to study the variations of 'a', 'm' and 'n' constants of Bhattacharya's equation², at different dilutions of the sol, and also at different periods of dialysis. The values of these constants have also been evaluated in presence of different non-electrolytes to throw light on the stabilising or sensitising power of the non-electrolytes used.

EXPERIMENTAL

40 gms of sodium stannate were dissolved in 500 ml doubly distilled water. To this solution was added a concentrated solution of sodium bicarbonate. The white precipitate, which formed on the addition of NaHCO₃ solution, was filtered off and washed with hot water. The precipitate was then transferred in a 1 litre beaker and 2 ml strong ammonia was added. After the mixture had stood for about 10 minutes, it was made to 1 litre with doubly distilled water. The sol was then put to dialysis in a parchment paper bag. Three different samples of the sol were prepared. One sample was used for the study of the effect of dilution, the second for the effect of dialysis and the third for the study of non-electrolyte effect.

Time of coagulation of the sol, using NaCl and KCl as coagulating electrolytes, was determined by Light Extinction Method, using a Gallenkamp photoelectric Colorimeter and the constants (a, m and n) were found graphically³. The values of the constants obtained for the same stage of coagulation given by the same extinction value for the sol at different stages of dilution and dialysis, and also in the presence of different amounts of various non-electrolytes have been recorded in tables I, II and III.

1. M. Singh and O. P. Bansal, *this journal*, 1966, 43, 287, 316.
2. A. K. Bhattacharya *et al.*, *this journal*, 1951, 28, 179, 638; 1952, 29, 687, 759, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1955, 10, 551.
3. A. K. Bhattacharya *et al.*, *Agra Univ. J. Res. Sci.*, 1963, 12, 101; *J. Colloid. Sci.*, 1956, 11, 124.

TABLE I

Concentration of the sol (A) = 10.00 g SnO₂/litre (Dialysed)
Effect of dilution

Electrolyte used	Sol	κ (mM/l)		m (mM/l)			n (min. ⁻¹)		
		A/A/2	A/4	Sol A	A/2	A/4	Sol A	A/2	A/4
NaCl	40.0	45.0	55.0	32.28	32.258	27.80	0.0623	0.0564	0.03
KCl	75.0	77.0	80.0	50.0	41.70	40.0	0.2417	0.133	0.10

TABLE II

Effect of dialysis

Sol dialysed for (days)	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$ (mhos)	κ (mM/l)		m (mM/l)		n (min. ⁻¹)	
		NaCl	KCl	NaCl	KCl	NaCl	KCl
2	21.15	100	500	104.17	444.4	—	—
4	9.40	80	200	83.30	300.0	0.0530	0.0950
6	6.50	70	120	51.28	161.3	0.0308	0.0645
8	5.12	55	80	41.70	100.0	0.0208	0.0340
10	4.12	50	60	30.00	71.4	0.0200	0.0250
12	3.93	40	50	22.20	41.7	0.0190	0.0200

TABLE III

Effect of non-electrolytes

		κ (mM/l)		m (mM/l)		n (min. ⁻¹)	
		NaCl	KCl	NaCl	KCl	NaCl	KCl
Ethanol	(0.1 ml)	40	70	23.023	38.46	0.0108	0.0333
"	(0.2 ")	30	60	27.00	32.26	0.0100	0.017
"	(0.3 ")	20	50	31.25	24.00	0.0080	0.0120
"	(0.4 ")	10	40	34.483	20.83	0.0057	0.0072
Acetone	(0.1 ml)	45	60	19.60	43.50	0.0112	0.0170
"	(0.2 ")	35	50	21.70	41.70	0.0107	0.0145
"	(0.3 ")	25	45	26.31	41.70	0.0098	0.0140
"	(0.4 ")	15	35	31.25	33.33	0.0091	0.0117
Dioxane	(0.1 ml)	35	50	26.31	51.28	0.0079	0.0128
"	(0.2 ")	25	40	29.41	48.80	0.0073	0.0122
"	(0.3 ")	15	30	32.25	48.80	0.0040	0.0120
"	(0.4 ")	5	20	36.36	46.51	0.0035	0.0116
Pure sol without non-electrolytes	50	75	27.80	50.00	0.0229	0.0440	
Urea 5 M (0.5 ml)	50	80	27.80	47.62	0.0229	0.0460	
" "	(1.0 ")	52.5	80	29.41	47.62	0.0291	0.0460
Glycerol (0.5 ml.)	50	90	27.80	62.50	0.0229	0.0710	
"	(0.8 ")	60	105	23.03	50.0	0.0231	0.0520
"	(1.1 ")	65	115	21.30	50.0	0.0260	0.0610
"	(1.4 ")	70	125	29.41	55.55	0.0235	0.0680

DISCUSSION

Bhattacharya's equation, $C = a + \frac{m \cdot 1/t}{n + 1/t}$ may be put in the form $1/c - a = (n/m) t + 1/m$ which shows that the plot $1/c - a$ against t should be a straight line and this has actually been observed in all cases of the present studies (figs. not given for the economy of the space) confirming the applicability of the equation for the coagulation of the sol by electrolytes, in the partially dialysed state and also in presence of non-electrolytes.

Table 1 shows that the value of 'a', the critical stability concentration of the electrolyte for the sol, increases with the dilution of the highly purified sol.

If $1/t$ is made large as compared to 'n', the equation, $C = a + \frac{m \cdot 1/t}{n + 1/t}$, takes up the form, $C = a + m$. This means that 'm' is the excess of the electrolyte that should be added above the critical stability concentration 'a', in order to cause the immediate coagulation of the sol. It may be said that at $C = a + m$, the region of slow coagulation merges into that of rapid coagulation. From table 1, it is evident that the value of $(a + m)$ increases with dilution of the sol indicating that the region of slow coagulation merges into that of rapid coagulation earlier in the concentrated purified stannic hydroxide sol. From this, it appears that the highly purified stannic hydroxide sol becomes more stabilised on dilution. Similar observation was also obtained by Sorum⁴ for $Cr(OH)_3$ and $Fe(OH)_3$ sols.

The values of the constants a, m and n decrease with the progressive dialysis of the sol (table II). The values of 'a', the critical stability concentration, and of m, the concentration of the electrolyte above the critical value to cause instantaneous coagulation, have been found to decrease rapidly in the initial period of dialysis (2 to 6 days), but on further dialysis the fall becomes gradual. As the dialysis of the sol continues, its stabilising electrolyte is removed and so it becomes increasingly sensitive and hence its region of slow coagulation merges into the rapid coagulation at lower concentration of the coagulating electrolyte, as evidenced by the decrease in the value of $(a + m)$, with the time of dialysis.

The non-electrolytes which sensitise the coagulation process of stannic hydroxide sol towards NaCl and KCl electrolytes are found to decrease the values of a, $a + m$, and n (table III). The extent of sensitisation by ethanol, acetone and dioxane is greater in presence of increasing volume of these non-electrolytes. On adding urea and glycerol, which have a stabilising effect, the value of a, $a + m$, and n increases instead of decreasing.

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